

Comprehensive model of human-clothing-environment system

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Introduction

Heat and mass transfer within a clothing system is a composition of a number of physical processes (Fig. 1). In addition, factors associated with construction and use of a garment, such as air penetration and compression by wind, body posture and movement and clothing fit, influence these processes significantly due to the changing size and shape of the layers. Therefore, for an evaluation of realistic effects of garments on the human body, the actual distribution of air layers within and around clothing needs to be considered, for example, by using the anatomically shaped manikin in a given posture and wearing properly selected size of an ensemble. The same principle applies to the analytical or numerical human thermoregulation and clothing models to ensure their accuracy. This paper introduces a comprehensive model of human-clothing-environment system which considers realistic spatial distribution of air layers in the clothing and effect of body shape simplification.

Figure 1. Heat transfer pathways at the human body surface and within the clothing layers [1].

Methods

The comprehensive model of human-clothing-environment system comprises a cascade of various individually developed and validated models (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The scheme of simulation order using a cascade of various models [2-9] as well as required and resultant input and output parameters.

Results and discussion

In the simulated example in Fig 3, the difference between the thermo-physiological responses for the assumed no-air-gap case is greatly different than that for the tight-fitting ensemble. Such substantial differences are physiologically relevant and may lead to false estimation of the resultant thermo-physiological state of the human body. Secondly, the effect of the clothing fit was evident in the thermo-physiological and sensational response beyond the statistical error, and hence, can be used to customize and to support the desired thermal clothing effects. These differences would become more critical towards more extreme scenarios with higher metabolic rates, more water vapour impermeable clothing and more extreme ambient temperatures.

Conclusions

This detailed comprehensive model of human-clothing-environment system shall contribute to the improvement of the evaluation of energy-saving conditioning technologies, and enhance the clothing design for protective and functional apparel to balance the environmental and bodily influence on clothing performance.

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Figure 3. Mean skin, body core, upper back and lumbus skin temperatures, dynamic thermal sensation and skin wetness predicted for assumed no air gap case and an realistic air gap distribution in tight- and loose-fitting ensembles for a combination of the environmental conditions (10 and 30°C) and activity level of 3met [7].